

Supercritical CO₂ extraction behavior of electrolyte solvents from Li-ion battery black mass

Nils Zachmann^{*}

Department of Chemistry and Chemical Engineering, Chalmers University of Technology, Kemivägen 4, Gothenburg SE-412 96, Sweden

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ABSTRACT

Electrolyte recovery from spent Li-ion batteries remains a significant challenge in the current recycling process. Li-ion battery waste streams containing electrolyte residues are classified as hazardous waste and entail a financial and workplace safety burden for the recycling industry. Recent studies show the potential use of supercritical CO₂ extraction for the recovery of electrolyte solvents. In this study, the extraction behavior of electrolyte solvents from Li-ion battery black mass using supercritical CO₂ process under pressures of 100 and 140 bar at 40°C was investigated. The extraction yield of dimethyl carbonate, ethyl methyl carbonate, and diethyl carbonate exceeded 99 % at both pressures. Ethylene carbonate, biphenyl, and propylene carbonate were successfully extracted with an extraction yield exceeding 95 % using 140 bar and 40°C. The extraction rates of biphenyl, ethylene carbonate and propylene carbonate at 140 bar and 40°C in the linear extraction regime of the extraction curve were determined to be 0.18 mg/g CO₂, 1.9 mg/g CO₂ and 0.4 mg/g CO₂, respectively. The research demonstrates that supercritical CO₂ processing is a highly promising method not only for recycling electrolytes but also for mitigating the hazardous risks associated with battery waste.

1. Introduction

The safe and environmentally friendly recovery of the electrolyte is a key factor in the Li-ion battery (LiB) recycling process [1]. The state-of-the-art non-aqueous liquid electrolyte is composed of a conductive salt (i.e., lithium hexafluorophosphate, LiPF₆) dissolved in a combination of organic solvents (i.e., dimethyl carbonate (DMC), ethyl methyl carbonate (EMC), ethylene carbonate (EC)) and additives (i.e., propylene carbonate (PC), biphenyl, fluoroethylene carbonate, vinylene carbonate). Most of these components are (highly) volatile, flammable, and classified [2–5]. An overview of the most common electrolyte solvents and their specific hazard is given in Table S1 in the supplementary material. An uncontrolled release in the LiB recycling plant can potentially have a serious impact on the workers' health and the environment [5,6]. Moreover, LiB waste streams containing electrolyte residues are classified as hazardous waste and entail a financial burden for the recycling industry in respect of transportation, and high processing costs [1,7]. Once successfully recovered, extensive purification steps of the collected products are often required for the electrolyte to be saleable for reuse in the battery manufacturing process or repurpose in other industries [8].

Several pre-treatment steps, i.e., sorting, discharging, dismantling, crushing, shredding, grinding, magnetic/ air separation, and/or sieving are used in a LiB recycling process to receive a mixture containing mainly the cathode and anode active material known as black mass [8, 9]. A separate pre-treatment step is then required to completely recover the electrolyte from the black mass. Typically, (vacuum) vaporization is employed to separate the electrolyte from the rest of the LiB waste material after the shredding stage. Thereby, the commonly used conductive salt LiPF₆ decomposes to corrosive gaseous hydrofluoric acid and other toxic organo-fluorophosphates, which leads to a major safety risk in the recycling process [6,10,11]. Alternatively, the electrolyte can be recovered using solvent extraction or supercritical carbon dioxide (scCO₂) extraction [1,12–14]. An advantage of using scCO₂ extraction compared to (vacuum) vaporization processes is that thermal unstable LiPF₆ does not decompose but remains intact during the extraction process [15].

Carbon dioxide (CO₂) becomes supercritical once the critical pressure (73.8 bar) and temperature (31.1°C) is exceeded. In this state, CO₂ behaves like a gas i.e., gas-like diffusivity coefficients, and a liquid i.e., liquid-like viscosity, while having neglectable surface tension. By varying the pressure and temperature conditions, the solvent properties

^{*} Corresponding author.

E-mail address: zachmann@chalmers.se (N. Zachmann).

of scCO₂ can be fine-tuned for the extraction of a variety of organic compounds. Thus, the scCO₂ extraction is a predestined alternative due to its easily adjustable properties and excellent mass-transfer characteristics. However, CO₂ is a non-polar solvent, and thus the extraction of polar compounds is limited. Their extraction yields can be increased in combination with a suitable co-solvent typically less than 5 % [16–18]. Thereby, the scCO₂ provides the supercritical phase, whereas the co-solvent-solute interactions contribute to the increased solubility of the polar compounds [19,20]. On the other hand, the co-solvent may influence the solute availability in the matrix. However, adding a co-solvent comes with disadvantages. As both the co-solvent and extracts are collected in the separator, further purification stages are required to obtain a pure extract.

In literature, the potential of scCO₂ extraction to recover electrolyte from LiB waste was investigated to evaluate the implementation of the technology [21–28]. The studies demonstrated that the non-polar electrolyte solvents DMC, EMC, and DEC can be extracted from separator materials with high yields using scCO₂ (150 – 350 bar, 30 – 50°C) [24]. Grützke et al. [22] reported low electrolyte extraction yields of less than 50 % from commercially sold 18650 cells using liquid CO₂ (60 bar, 25°C). Even lower yields were obtained under scCO₂ (300 bar, 40°C) conditions. The extraction yield was enhanced to 89 % by adding a co-solvent mixture (acetonitrile and propylene carbonate, 3:1) to liquid CO₂ (60 bar, 40°C). However, there is still a lack of research that studies the mass-transfer mechanism of the different electrolyte solvents at mild scCO₂ extraction conditions (<160 bar, <60°C). Knowledge of the mass-transfer mechanism is important when designing the recycling process to achieve high extraction yields while minimizing the CO₂ consumption and extraction time. Thus, the objective of this study was to understand the extraction behavior of the electrolyte from LiB black mass to eventually obtain electrolyte free LiB waste. Therefore, the extraction curves of the remaining electrolyte solvent components DMC, EMC, DEC, EC, PC, and biphenyl were studied at two different pressures (100 bar and 140 bar) at 40°C. A general model derived by Sovová [29] was then used to determine the partition coefficient and mass-transfer coefficient from EC and PC.

2. Theoretical

In this study, the generalized model derived by Sovová was used to fit the extraction curves [29]. The model enables simulation of different types of extraction curves and characterizes them with mutually comparable parameters such as mass-transfer coefficients and equilibrium constants.

The scCO₂ extraction process can be divided into two extraction stages [29–31]. The first stage is controlled by the phase equilibrium between the solid and the fluid phase. The second period is governed by mass transfer (internal diffusion). By plotting the cumulative extraction yield versus the consumed solvent or extraction time, the extraction process and stages can be characterized. In the first stage of the extraction process, the easily accessible solute on the particle surface transfers to the scCO₂ phase in an amount restricted by the solubility of the solute in the scCO₂. This stage is reassembled in the extraction curve as a constant slope, which is related to the solute solubility. In the presence of solute-matrix interactions, the slope is a magnitude lower than the solubility and is called apparent solubility. The extraction rate, defined as the amount of substance extracted per unit of time or solvent quantity, decreases continuously in the second stage of the extraction process. This decrease occurs because there is not enough easily accessible solute left on the particle surface, and due to mass-transfer constraints from the core particle to its surface. Finally, the extraction curve completely flattens out and reaches the total extractable amount present in the sample at the specific scCO₂ condition [32].

The model assumes that the solute is homogeneously distributed in the untreated solid. The solute particles contain an easily accessible solute fraction close to its surface and a less accessible solute at its core.

The latter is believed to first diffuse from the core to the particle surface, whereby the mass transfer is characterized by the solid-phase mass-transfer coefficient. The solute is assumed to be transferred directly from the surface to the fluid-phase and the mass transfer is characterized by the fluid-phase mass transfer coefficient. Furthermore, it is assumed that the fluid density is not affected by the dissolved solute as well as the surface area, void fraction, and extraction bed characteristics.

Large discrepancies in mass-transfer coefficients enable the splitting of the extraction curve into two parts. The straight part is mainly governed by the phase equilibrium and is flow pattern dependent, while internal mass transfer controls the shape of the second part, the curved line. With respect to the discontinuity and the initial composition of the solid and liquid phase, the model defines four different types of extraction curves, labelled A-D, which are illustrated in Figure S1 in the supplementary material [29].

The extraction curves belonging to Type A represent the scenario in which the fluid-phase equilibrium is independent of solute-matrix interactions and is equal to the solubility. Extraction curves of Type B and C have two straight sections instead of one, as in these cases, the solute is both free but also interacts with the matrix. Type B and C extraction curves differ based on the amount of solvent passed through the extraction bed at the second straight section. In Type C extraction curves, the second straight section starts very early, typically, as soon as the solvent that filled the extraction bed in the static extraction period left the bed. In Type D, the fluid-phase equilibrium is controlled by solute-matrix interactions and the linear relationship between the solid- and fluid-phase equilibrium gives rise to the partition coefficient.

The recommended procedure to evaluate equilibrium extraction curves is to first identify the type of extraction curve that fits the retrieved extraction data. When the first part of the extraction curve consists of only one straight section, the extraction curve is of Type A or D. As the Type A extraction curve describes an extraction without solute-matrix interaction, it can be differentiated from the Type D extraction by knowledge of the approximate solubility of the free solute. If the initial slope is close to the solubility of the free solute and there is a sharp transition between the first and the second part of the extraction curve, it is Type A. Otherwise, it is Type D. If there are two straight sections observable, it is of Type B, or C. One can differentiate Type B and C by the amount of solvent passed through the extraction bed by the intersection between the first and second straight line. After identifying the type of extraction curve, the first straight part of the extraction curve can be fitted using an appropriate model. In this study, the extraction curves were modelled using the model equation of type D as solute-matrix interactions had to be considered as discussed in more detail in the result section.

Type D extraction curves are modeled by fitting a straight line to the first part of the extraction curve using Eq. 1 [29].

$$e = \frac{Kx_u}{1 + K(\frac{r}{\gamma})} q = y_0 q \text{ for } 0 \leq q \leq q_c \quad (1)$$

Whereas e is the extraction yield (kg (extract) kg (solid)⁻¹), q is the relative amount of passed solvent (kg (solvent) kg (solid)⁻¹), q_c is the coordinate of the crossing point of part 1 and part 2 (kg (solvent) kg (solid)⁻¹), x_u is the solute concentration in the untreated solid (kg (solute) kg (solid)⁻¹), γ is the solvent-to-matrix ratio in the bed (kg (solvent) kg (solid)⁻¹), K is the partition coefficient, r is the easily accessible solute fraction and y_0 is the initial fluid phase concentration (kg (solute) kg (solid)⁻¹).

The second part of the extraction curve can be then fitted using Eq. 2.

$$e = x_u [1 - C_1 \exp(-C_2 q)] \text{ for } 0 \leq q \leq q_c \quad (2)$$

The model parameters C_1 and C_2 are then used to determine the fraction of easily accessible solute fraction, r , and solid-phase mass-transfer coefficient, $k_{s,as}$, according to

$$r = 1 - C_1 \exp(-C_2 q_c) \quad (3)$$

$$k_{s_2} = \frac{(1-r)(1-\varepsilon)QC_2}{N_m \left[1 - \left(\frac{1-r}K C_2\right)\right]} \text{ for } x_t > 0 \quad (4)$$

whereas ε is the bed void fraction, Q is the solvent flowrate, and N_m is the charge of insoluble solid. N_m itself can be determined according to

$$N_m = (1 - c_u)N \quad (5)$$

Whereas c_u is the solute share in the untreated solid ($\frac{x_u}{1+x_u}$), and N is the solid charge in the extractor.

3. Experimental

3.1. Materials

Liquid carbon dioxide with a purity of $\geq 99.99\%$ was purchased from Air Liquide. Acetonitrile (ACN, $>99.9\%$), nitric acid (HNO₃, $>65\%$), DMC ($>99\%$), EMC ($>99\%$), DEC ($>99\%$), EC ($>98\%$), PC (99%), and biphenyl ($>99\%$) were purchased from Merck Millipore. The LiB waste was pretreated by SK TES in France through a series of proprietary processing stages, including a controlled shredding step in an inert atmosphere to reduce fire risks, followed by a series of physical separation steps to produce black mass [33]. The black mass sample was received from the stated partner and used without any further treatment in the experiments. The general steps performed by the industrial partner to obtain the black mass included pre-shredding, magnetic separation, air separation, vibration separation, and dust recovery.

3.2. Experimental procedures

3.2.1. Determination of electrolyte composition in the black mass

The electrolyte content remaining in the LiB black mass was determined using an adapted procedure described by Peschel et al. [34]. The black mass (3.00 ± 0.02 g) was placed as received inside a 50 ml plastic vial and 5 ml of acetonitrile was added. After shaking by hand for 5 min, the extraction solution was filtered and analyzed using gas chromatography – mass spectroscopy (GC-MS) and inductively coupled plasma – optical emission spectroscopy (ICP-OES) after dilution of the extraction solution using a dilution factor of 10, and 200, respectively. To determine the amount of not-extracted electrolyte during the scCO₂ extraction process, 2.00 ± 0.02 g of the scCO₂ treated black mass was used using the previously described method.

3.2.2. scCO₂ extraction process

3.2.2.1. Set-up. The set-up used for the scCO₂ extraction is illustrated in Figure S2. CO₂ was brought into the supercritical state at the required pressure and temperature conditions using a syringe pump system (ISCO 260D, Teledyne ISCO) connected to an external thermostat (Model F10 & CM, Julabo). The in-house build stainless-steel extraction chamber (volume (18 ml), length (15 cm), inner (1.24 cm) and outer diameter (1.27 cm), frit filter (2 μ m)) was pressurized using manual valves and thermostated using water pipes, connected to an external thermostat (Model F12 & ED, Julabo). A thermocouple and a manometer were used to monitor the temperature and pressure within the extraction chamber. The flow rate was controlled by a meter valve (SS-S2, Swagelok) and monitored using a mass flowmeter (red-y smart meter GSM, Vögtlin instruments) connected at ambient conditions ($22 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$, 1 bar) right before the exhaust gas was released to the room pressure environment. The meter valve temperature was controlled to $40 \pm 5^\circ\text{C}$ using an electric temperature controller (W-510, Winkler) to avoid freezing the CO₂. The extracts were adsorbed in two consecutive collection vials filled with acetonitrile, which were placed in an ice-bath. The first collection vial contained 5 ml of acetonitrile, and the second collection vial 25 ml of acetonitrile. After the collection vials, two gas washing

bottles (one empty and one filled with 50 ml of MQ water) were connected before the passed CO₂ was measured using the mass flowmeter.

3.2.2.2. Extraction procedure. The received black mass was a fine powder with particle size less than 0.4 mm. Thus, to prevent channeling effects inside the equilibrium cell, the designated amount of black mass (3, 6, or 9 g, with uncertainties of ± 0.05 g) was mixed with an appropriate amount of glass beads ($d = 2$ mm) to fill the extractor. Then, the extraction chamber was charged with the mixture and leak tight closed with wrenches. The extraction chamber temperature was 40°C . After the temperature and pressure were stabilized to the extraction conditions for 7.5 min, a constant flow rate was applied, and the extract was adsorbed within the collection vials. The CO₂ mass flow was 3.5 ± 0.5 g/min at 100 bar, and 7.6 ± 0.5 g/min at 140 bar. The CO₂ consumed during the extraction process was monitored at depressurized conditions (1 bar, $22 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$) using a mass flow meter. For every 5 L of CO₂, measured at ambient conditions, static extraction was applied for 1 min to change the first collection vial until a total CO₂ consumption of 65 L was reached. The CO₂ consumption was converted from liter into gram by multiplication of the calibration density of 1.977 g/L, which was provided by the mass flow meter software. Then, the extraction chamber was depressurized. The collection solution was subsequently quantitatively analyzed with GC-MS, and ICP-OES. After the scCO₂ extraction process, the black mass was separated from the glass beads by sieving. A part of the scCO₂ treated black mass (2.00 ± 0.02 g) was used to determine the residual content of electrolyte using the method described in section 2.2.1 and for thermogravimetric analysis (TGA). All the experiments were performed in triplicate.

4. Measurement and characterization

The extraction yield percentage of the different electrolyte components were calculated based on the reference extraction using acetonitrile before and after the scCO₂ extraction according to Eq. (6):

$$E\% = \left(1 - \frac{m_{\text{after}}}{m_{\text{initial}}}\right) \times 100 \quad (6)$$

where $E\%$ is the extraction yield percentage, m_{initial} is the initial electrolyte component content in the black mass, and m_{after} is the residual electrolyte component content in the scCO₂ treated black mass. The electrolyte component content determination is described in Section 2.2.1.

Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA, Q500, TA Instruments) was performed to determine the initial electrolyte content in the retrieved LiB black mass. The temperature was ramped at a rate of $5^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$ from 20°C to 300°C at a constant N₂ flow of 100 ml/min. TGA analysis was performed before and after the scCO₂ extraction process to determine the overall extraction yield. The TGA analysis of the initial black mass was performed in triplicate.

GC-MS (GC-2030 NX, GCMS-QP2020 NX, Shimadzu) with a Zebron ZB-5MS column (30 m x 250 μ m x 0.25 μ m) was used to quantitatively analyze the extract solutions. The samples were automatically injected with a split ratio of 1:20 and a purge flow of 3 ml/min. The temperature of the injection and transfer line were 270°C and 230°C , respectively. Helium was used as carrier gas at a flowrate of 1 ml/min. The GC oven temperature was maintained at 40°C for 1 min and then ramped at $20^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$ to 260°C , which was maintained for 2 min. MS conditions were electron impact, ionization source temperature 230°C , 70 eV filament voltage, mass range 30–300 m/z . The integrated areas from EC (43 m/z), PC (57 m/z), EMC (77 m/z), DMC (45 m/z), DEC (45 m/z), and biphenyl (154 m/z) were used for quantification, whereas the quantification ions are given in brackets. Acetonitrile was used to prepare a standard series with concentrations of 10, 25, 50, 100, 200, 500, 1000, and 2000 mg/L mixed standard solutions. To obtain the cumulative yield of the extraction curve, the determined masses were added

up.

ICP-OES (ThermoFisher Scientific, iCAP PRO) was used for elemental analysis of the extracted solution after the acetonitrile extraction of the untreated and scCO₂ treated black mass. Prior to the analysis, the samples were diluted in 0.5 M HNO₃ with a dilution factor of 200. Yttrium was used as an internal standard. Standards containing Li, Ni, Co, Mn, Fe, Cu, Al, P, Na, S, Si, Cd, Ca, and Zn were prepared by dilution in 0.5 M HNO₃ for the linear range calibration between 0.3 and 20 ppm. The approximate detection limit was 0.1 ppm.

BET analysis (Micromeritics ASAP 2020 Surface Area and Porosity Analyzer) was conducted to measure the specific surface area of the black mass particles using a 5 point N₂ adsorption isotherm method. Before the BET analysis was performed, the BM sample was dried under vacuum at 130°C overnight. The average particle size of the black mass sample was then estimated according to Eq. (7), assuming black mass particles have spherical morphology.

$$D = \frac{6000}{S_{\text{BET}}\rho_{\text{BM}}} \quad (7)$$

Where D (in nm) is the average particle diameter, S_{BET} is the BET specific surface area (in m²/g), and ρ_{BM} (in g/cm³) is the density of the black mass.

The density of the black mass was measured using a gas pycnometer (Micromeritics AccuPyc II 1340).

5. Results and discussion

5.1. Electrolyte content and composition remaining in the black mass

Before the remaining electrolyte content and composition in the black mass were analyzed, the average particle diameter of the black mass was estimated based on the BET specific surface area (11.18 ± 0.02 m²/g), and the density of the black mass (3.11 ± 0.03 g/cm³). According to Eq. 7, the average particle diameter of the black mass was 172 ± 2 nm.

The remaining electrolyte content and composition in the LiB black mass were characterized using TGA, GC-MS, and ICP-OES. TGA was used to determine the weight percentage of residual electrolyte in the black mass sample. The mass loss of the sample in the range between room temperature and 150°C can be attributed to the removal of the electrolyte solvents and degradation of LiPF₆ [10]. According to TGA, the mass loss at 150°C was 5.7 ± 0.5 wt%, as presented in Figure S3. This corresponds to a total amount of 57 ± 5 mg of electrolyte per g of black

mass. However, the estimated electrolyte amount might also include moisture absorbed during the black mass production process due to its hygroscopic nature. The remaining electrolyte composition in the black mass was quantified via a reference extraction using acetonitrile as the extraction solvent. The extract solution was subsequently analyzed using GC-MS and ICP-OES. The chromatogram of the extraction solution is plotted in Fig. 1. The peaks with the highest area were assigned to DMC (1), EMC (2), DEC (4), EC (6), PC (8), and biphenyl (16), and their determined quantitative amounts, stated in mg per g of black mass, are presented in Table 1. Other peaks, such as peak 5, 11, 12, 14, and 15 are carbonates, potentially formed during the decomposition of the electrolyte components [35–37]. However, it must be mentioned that not all peaks could be successfully assigned to their corresponding chemical structure. The assigned peaks together with their retention times and their characteristic ion peaks are listed in Table S2 in the supplementary material.

Unfortunately, the original electrolyte composition of the batteries used to produce the black mass was unknown. Typically, EC is blended with approximately 50–70 % of DMC, EMC, and/or DEC [38]. It can be observed that the ratio between the main electrolyte solvents DMC, EMC, DEC, and EC in the remaining black mass differs from the generally used ratios in fresh electrolyte solutions [39]. EC (22 ± 1 mg/g) was the main residual electrolyte solvent in the black mass, followed by PC

Table 1

Estimated electrolyte solvent content (in mg) per g of black mass of DMC, EMC, DEC, EC, PC and biphenyl based on the GC-MS, and ICP-OES analysis of the acetonitrile extraction. ^a Average of 5 samples. ^b Uncertainty (±) is expressed as the standard deviation (1σ) of 5 extraction samples. 'Other' Corresponds to the differences between quantified compounds and total electrolyte content determined by TGA analysis.

	Content (mg/g)
DMC	0.12 ^a ± 0.05 ^b
EMC	0.5 ± 0.1
DEC	0.25 ± 0.05
PC	1.6 ± 0.1
Biphenyl	0.6 ± 0.1
EC	22 ± 1
LiPF ₆	15.4 ± 0.3
Other	16 ± 5
Total	57 ± 5

Fig. 1. Chromatogram of the extraction using acetonitrile. The corresponding peak assignments are given in table S1.

(1.6 ± 0.1 mg/g) and biphenyl (0.6 ± 0.1 mg/g) as can be seen in Table 1. The low contents of PC, and biphenyl suggest that they were additives in the original electrolyte solution [38,40]. The presence of EC, PC, and biphenyl in the black mass is due to their lower vapor pressure compared to DMC, EMC, and DEC. It is assumed that the majority of volatile solvents DMC, DEC, and EMC evaporated during the shredding and physical separation stages to produce the black mass by the industrial partner while EC, PC, and biphenyl remained in the black mass as reported in different studies [41,42].

Subsequently to the GC-MS analysis, ICP-OES analysis was performed to determine the metallic impurities in the extracted electrolyte composition. P (3.2 ± 0.3 mg/g), Li (0.71 ± 0.01 mg/g), S (0.15 ± 0.03 mg/g), Cu (0.20 ± 0.04 mg/g), and Na (0.07 ± 0.03 mg/g) were detected in the extract solution. All other analyzed elements (Ni, Co, Mn, Fe, Al, Si, Cd, Ca, and Zn) were below the detection limit. To verify that Li and P originated from the extraction of LiPF₆, the mass ratio between P and Li was used. The calculated mass ratio of 4.75 was slightly higher than the mass ratio expected in LiPF₆ (4.46). This indicated a higher amount of P compared to Li in the sample, which can originate from organo-fluorophosphates formed from degraded LiPF₆ products or P-containing electrolyte additives [35,40,43]. The amount of remaining LiPF₆ in the black mass was estimated to be 15.4 ± 0.3 mg/g, based on the measured amount of Li and its theoretical mass percent in LiPF₆.

5.2. Extraction of electrolyte solvents using scCO₂

Two different pressure conditions (100 bar and 140 bar at 40°C, respectively) were compared for the extraction of the residual electrolyte solvents from the LiB black mass. The lower pressure limit (100 bar) for the extraction was selected based on binary phase-diagram literature data of DMC, EMC, and DEC [44–46]. These indicate that 100 bar, and 40°C is slightly above the critical point of the binary mixture, meaning CO₂ is miscible with DMC, EMC, and DEC. The upper pressure limit (140 bar) was selected based on a recently published article reporting promising solubility values (6.4 g/kg CO₂) of EC in CO₂ [47]. Moreover, 140 bar was also the upper pressure limit of the system used in this study, restricted by the valves.

Therefore, 3 g of the black mass was inserted along with an appropriate amount of glass beds into the extraction chamber. The cumulative extraction yield per g of black mass over the relatively passed CO₂ amount at both extraction conditions is plotted in Fig. 2. The data presented in the graph is according to the collected extracts in the collection chamber. An overview of the collected amount of the electrolyte solvents during the extraction runs is given in Table S3 in the supplementary material. Cleaning of the pipelines after the scCO₂ extraction procedure using acetonitrile showed that EC (5 ± 2 mg) partly

Fig. 2. Cumulative extraction yield in mg/g of black mass over the relative passed CO₂ amount (g/g of black mass) at 100 bar (blue) and 140 bar (Orange) and 40°C. The uncertainty bars represent the standard deviation (1σ , $n = 3$).

precipitated during the collection process in the exhaust outlet and thus was not collected in the extraction chamber. To obtain the cumulative extraction yield, the collected amounts of EC, PC, DMC, EMC, DEC, and biphenyl were added for each sampling point. The cumulative extraction yield of the electrolyte solvents at 140 bar (18 ± 1 mg/g of black mass) was higher than at 100 bar (7 ± 1 mg/g of black mass) using the same quantity of relatively passed CO₂ (42 g CO₂/g of black mass). At 140 bar the extraction behavior was linear at first until the second sampling point at 7 g CO₂/g of black mass. This part of the extraction curve represents the apparent solubility of the extracts [32]. Then, the extraction rate slowly decreased to eventually reach the maximum extraction yield. The slow decrease in extraction yield arises from the fact that there are no free solutes left on the surface particles, intra-particle mass transfer constraints, and/or solute-matrix interactions that impact the equilibrium [32]. An almost constant slope at 100 bar (Fig. 2) indicates that the easily extractable solutes have not been completely extracted due to their lower solubility in CO₂ at 100 bar compared to 140 bar.

Acetonitrile extraction and TGA analysis were performed on the scCO₂ treated black mass samples to determine the non-extracted electrolyte content. Based on these results, the electrolyte extraction yield percentage at 100 bar and 140 bar were determined using Eq. 6 as stated in Table 2. As observed, DMC, EMC, and DEC were successfully extracted from the black mass at 100 bar and 40°C, exceeding an extraction yield percentage of 99 %, respectively. According to the binary vapor-liquid phase diagrams of DMC, EMC, DEC, and CO₂, the solutes are miscible with CO₂ at the used extraction conditions (100 bar, 40 °C) [44–46]. The extraction yield percentage of biphenyl was 97 %. The extraction of the non-volatile, polar substances EC and PC at 100 bar, on the other hand, was limited with an extraction yield percentage of 60 % and 50 %, respectively. Raising the pressure to 140 bar, while using the same quantity of CO₂ led to an extraction yield percentage increase for EC and PC to 95 %, and 98 %, respectively. The increase in extraction yield percentage can be linked to the higher solubility of EC, and PC in CO₂ at 140 bar compared to 100 bar. According to our recent publication, the solubility of EC at 140 bar, and 40°C was 6.4 g/kg CO₂, whereas at 100 bar the solubility was 3.5 g/kg CO₂ [47]. Less than 5 % of the estimated quantity of LiPF₆ was extracted during the process.

Even though EC and PC are polar, they were successfully extracted with scCO₂ without the addition of a co-solvent. Literature has provided insights into the understanding of the solvation of esters in scCO₂ at a molecular level [19,48]. EC, and PC are all carbonate esters containing a carbonyl group (C=O) flanked by two alkoxy groups (R-O-). Two different stable solvation configurations, called Type I and Type II, ascribed to Lewis acid-base (LA-LB) interactions between the carbon atom of the CO₂ molecule and carbonyl oxygen, and ester oxygen,

Table 2

Extraction yield percentage for the different electrolyte components at 100 bar and 140 bar at 40°C determined based on the reference extraction using acetonitrile. The total amount of CO₂ during the extraction was 128 ± 1 g. this correlates to 40 ± 0.5 g CO₂/g black mass for the extraction at 100 bar using 3 g of black mass, and 14.5 ± 0.5 g CO₂/g black mass at 140 bar using 9 g of black mass. 'Other' Corresponds to the differences between quantified compounds and total electrolyte content determined by TGA analysis.

Electrolyte component	Extraction yield percentage (%)	
	@100 bar	@140 bar
DMC	99.5 ± 0.5	99.5 ± 0.5
EMC	99.5 ± 0.5	99.5 ± 0.5
DEC	99.5 ± 0.5	99.5 ± 0.5
PC	50 ± 3	98 ± 1
Biphenyl	97 ± 1	98 ± 1
EC	55 ± 5	95 ± 2
LiPF ₆	2 ± 1	2 ± 1
Other	55 ± 5	72 ± 5
Total	46 ± 3	65 ± 5

respectively, were described in literature. In the type I configuration, the carbonyl oxygen is solvated by the CO₂ molecule, whereas in the type II configuration, the CO₂ molecule is in vicinity of the ester oxygen. An illustration is given in Figure S4 to exemplify the two different stable solvation configurations Type I and Type II between CO₂ and esters using DMC. The presence of a methyl group leads to cooperative hydrogen bonding between the oxygen atom of the CO₂ molecule and H-atom of the methyl group which strengthens the interaction of both configurations. This explains the higher solubility of DMC, EMC, and DEC in comparison with EC, and PC. Other functional groups attached to the ester oxygen, such as phenyls, were observed to cause steric hindrance resulting in lower interaction energies.

5.3. Analysis of the extraction behavior

To design an extraction process, knowledge about the apparent solubility of the extracts is important. The apparent solubility of the extracts can be determined from the slope of the linear zone in an extraction curve [32]. It is important to study whether CO₂ was saturated with the extracts during the extraction process to use the full capacity of CO₂ [49]. This can be done by comparing extraction curves with different solvent flow rate to feed ratios [50]. If the solvent was saturated, the slopes of the extraction curves are equal. The solvent flow rate to feed ratio can be varied by either increasing the mass load in the extraction chamber or by varying the flow rate. In this study, we kept the flow rate provided by the syringe pumps constant at its lowest possible value while varying the mass load of black mass in the extraction chamber from 3, 6, to 9 g. The retrieved extraction curves at different black mass charges are plotted in Fig. 3. According to the data, steeper slopes were observed with increasing black mass charge. This indicates that the passed CO₂ was not saturated with the solutes at a solid charge of 3 g, and 6 g but the excess amount of CO₂ simply bypassed the black mass. At a solid charge of 9 g, the extraction chamber was entirely packed with the black mass and the experimental limit of the mass loading was reached. The electrolyte content in the black mass was relatively low with around 5.7 %. At low initial content of solutes, the available free solutes are typically not enough to saturate the scCO₂ phase [32]. Larger residence times would be required to achieve saturation of the scCO₂ phase [50].

Based on the extraction curve for a mass load of 9 g, it can be observed that the linear part of the extraction curve has its break point at about 8 g CO₂/g of black mass at an extraction yield of 16 ± 2 mg/g of black mass and an extraction rate of 2.8 mg/g of CO₂. It was assumed that saturation was not achieved and thus the actual maximum achievable extraction rate at these conditions might likely be higher. In the second part, the mass transfer of the solutes through the core of the

Fig. 3. Cumulative extraction curves were obtained using different mass loads (3 g (blue), 6 g (Orange), 9 g (Green)) in the extraction chamber at 140 bar and 40°C. The uncertainty bars represent the standard deviation (1σ , $n = 3$).

particles towards the particle surface or other mass-transfer-hindering solute-matrix interactions slow down the extraction rate. To extract the remaining electrolyte, another 7 g CO₂/g of black mass was needed. Eventually, the maximum extraction yield of 20 ± 1 mg/g of black mass was achieved at 15 g CO₂ /g of black mass. It was determined that the overall electrolyte extraction yield increased with an increased black mass load due to the higher contact time between the solutes and the solvent.

The remaining electrolyte in the black mass contained both volatile (DMC, EMC, DEC) and non-volatile (EC, PC, biphenyl) substances. The fraction of volatile solvents was low compared to the fraction of non-volatile solvents, as presented in Table 1. Thus, the extraction of non-volatile substances likely occurred simultaneously with the extraction of the volatile substances. The fraction of EC is especially high and believed to strongly affect the extraction behavior observed in Figs. 2 and 3. Typically, based on the different solubilities of volatile and non-volatile compounds, the fraction of non-volatile substances in the extract increases with extraction time and with increasing pressure [50].

To study the individual extraction behavior of the different components, the extraction curves of DMC, EMC, DEC, PC, and biphenyl at 100 bar using 3 g of black mass are plotted in Fig. 4a, whereas the extraction curve of EC is plotted in Fig. 4b. Relating to the results shown in Fig. 4, it is apparent that the extraction of EC is the dominant component in the overall extraction curve of the electrolytes. While analyzing the extraction behavior of the different components, it can be observed that the extraction curves of the volatile non-polar electrolyte solvents (DMC, EMC, and DEC) level off after the first sampling point at 3.5 g CO₂/g of black mass due to the depletion of the easily extractable fraction. A correlation of the extraction rates of EC, PC and biphenyl with the presence of DMC, EMC, and DEC in the extraction chamber can be observed in Fig. 4a and b. The extraction rate of the compounds slightly decreased after 15 g CO₂ /g of black mass, which overlaps with the point at which DMC, EMC, and DEC were fully extracted. Thus, it is assumed that during the first period of extraction, the volatile non-polar solvents DMC, EMC, and DEC feature as an entrainer/co-solvent for the extraction of biphenyl, EC, and PC extraction at 100 bar.

The extraction curves of DMC, EMC, DEC, biphenyl, EC, and PC at 140 bar and 40°C using 9 g of black mass are plotted in Fig. 5. A similar extraction behavior compared to 100 bar was observed for DMC, EMC, and DEC. The cumulative yield leveled off after the first sampling point, this time at 1.1 g CO₂ /g of black mass. The extraction of biphenyl is linear with an extraction rate of 0.18 mg/g of CO₂ until 3.4 g CO₂ /g of black mass, before reaching its maximum extraction yield. The mole fraction solubility of biphenyl was reported to be 8.73×10^{-3} and 1.11×10^{-2} , measured at 40°C and 119 bar, and 149 bar, respectively [51]. The extraction rate of 0.18 mg/g of CO₂ corresponds to a mole fraction of 5.1×10^{-6} , which is 4 orders of magnitude lower than the solubility reported in the literature. The apparent solubility of solutes can be much lower than thermodynamic solubilities due to a low initial solute content in the black mass, interaction with the black mass and/or interactions between the solutes in the extraction mixture [32].

The extraction rate of EC levels off at 7.5 g CO₂/g of black mass and for PC at less than 5 g CO₂/g of black mass. The apparent solubility of EC was 1.9 mg/g CO₂ and for PC it was 0.4 mg/g CO₂. Thereafter, mass transfer of the solutes from the core of the particle to the particle surface slows down the extraction rate until reaching the maximum extraction yield at less than 15 g CO₂/g of black mass. 50 % of the consumed CO₂ extracts 70 % of EC and the second half is required to extract the remaining 30 % of EC.

5.4. Modelling of the extraction curves of EC, and PC

Even though the extraction curves shown in Fig. 5 might not represent saturation curves, the extraction curves of EC, and PC using 9 g of black mass were fitted to retrieve an estimate about the underlying mass transfer. The modeled extraction curves are plotted in Figure S5. The

Fig. 4. Cumulative extraction curve of a) DMC (blue), EMC (Orange), DEC (Green), biphenyl (red), PC (purple), and b) EC at 100 bar and 40°C obtained with 3 g of black mass. The uncertainty bars represent the standard deviation (1σ , $n = 3$).

Fig. 5. Cumulative extraction curve of a) DMC (blue), EMC (Orange), DEC (Green), biphenyl (red), PC (purple) and b) EC at 140 bar and 40°C obtained with 3 g of black mass. The uncertainty bars represent the standard deviation (1σ , $n = 3$).

shape of the extraction curves indicates that the extraction is of Type A or D, as the extraction curves can be divided into 2 different stages (a straight and a curved line). As discussed previously, solute-matrix interactions govern the extraction process and thus the extraction curve is of Type D. The equilibrium constant, y_0 , of the solutes was determined based on the slope of the first part of the extraction curve based on Eq. 1. The second part of the extraction curve was fitted using Eq. 2 by adjusting the constants C_1 , and C_2 . The *curve_fit* function included in the Python module *scipy.optimize* was used to determine the optimized model parameters stated in Table 2. The square root of the diagonal element of the covariance matrix corresponding to the fitting parameter was used to determine the standard deviation (1σ). From those constants, and the value of q_c , the crossing point of the two phases, r can be estimated using Eq. 3. Knowing r , the partition coefficient, K , can be estimated using Eq. 1. Finally, the solid-phase mass-transfer coefficient, k_{s,a_s} , was estimated using Eq. 4. The estimated parameters are presented in Table 3. The uncertainties for these were calculated from the fitting parameter uncertainties of y_0 , C_1 , and C_2 using the Gaussian error propagation. The easily accessible solute fraction of EC was estimated to be 61 %, whereas for PC 81 %. The partition coefficient, K , was estimated to be 0.137 for EC, and 0.338 for PC, and the solute-phase mass-transfer coefficient was estimated to be 0.089 s^{-1} for EC, and 0.019 s^{-1}

Table 3
Parameters determined using the Sovová model.

Model parameter	EC	PC
q_c (g CO ₂ /g black mass)	5.78	3.46
y_0 (mg/g CO ₂) ^a	1.92 ± 0.02	0.40 ± 0.03
C_1	1.8 ± 0.3	0.7 ± 0.2
C_2	0.3 ± 0.2	0.38 ± 0.06
r	0.61 ± 0.08	0.81 ± 0.06
K	0.137 ± 0.004	0.34 ± 0.03
k_{s,a_s} (s ⁻¹)	0.089	0.019

for PC.

6. Conclusion

The extraction behavior of the residual electrolyte in LiB black mass using scCO₂ extraction at different pressures (100 bar and 140 bar) at 40°C was studied. A total amount of 57 ± 5 mg of electrolyte per g of black mass was determined to be left in the black mass. The main constituents in the residual electrolyte were both volatile (DMC, EMC, DEC) and non-volatile (EC, PC, biphenyl) substances. EC (22 ± 1 mg/g) was the main residual electrolyte solvent in the black mass, followed by PC (1.6 ± 0.1 mg/g), biphenyl (0.6 ± 0.1 mg/g), EMC (0.5 ± 0.1 mg/g), DEC (0.25 ± 0.05 mg/g), and DMC (0.12 ± 0.05 mg/g). The amount of remaining LiPF₆ in the black mass was estimated to be 15.4 ± 0.3 mg/g. An overall higher electrolyte extraction yield was achieved using 140 bar compared to 100 bar at 40°C. The volatile electrolyte components DMC, EMC, DEC were already successfully extracted from the black mass using 100 bar 40°C with an extraction yield exceeding 99 %. Raising the pressure to 140 bar led to high extraction yields of biphenyl, EC, and PC with 98 %, 95 %, and 98 %, respectively. Whereas the electrolyte solvents were successfully extracted from the black mass, less than 5 % of the estimated quantity of LiPF₆ was extracted during the process at both pressure conditions. To achieve high extraction yields of the Li-salt, the use of a co-solvent is unavoidable. Analysis of the extraction behavior of the individual electrolyte solvents revealed that the extraction of the volatile electrolyte solvents was quick at both pressure conditions while having a similar extraction behavior. Furthermore, it could be observed that the volatile electrolyte solvents featured as an entrainer for the extraction of biphenyl, EC, and PC.

The electrolyte recycling process should result in a black mass without residual electrolyte solvents. The study successfully showed that electrolyte solvents can be successfully extracted from the black mass. EC was the electrolyte solvent with the highest remaining share in the

black mass and its extraction consumed the most CO₂. Modeling of the extraction curves at 140 bar and 40°C showed that the easily accessible EC fraction (60 %) was recovered after 5.78 g CO₂/g black mass. By increasing the mass load of the extraction chamber, the CO₂ eventually saturates with the electrolyte solvents and the overall CO₂ consumption can be potentially further reduced. However, the limiting factor in the extraction of the electrolyte solvents, especially EC, was the diffusion-controlled mass transfer. This dictates the required extraction time and results in a higher CO₂ throughput. The extraction rates of biphenyl, EC and PC in the solubility driven extraction regime were determined to be 0.18 mg/g CO₂, 1.9 mg/g CO₂ and 0.4 mg/g CO₂, respectively. For the upscaling of the process, the solid-phase mass transfer coefficient of EC, and PC are important, which were estimated to be 0.089 s⁻¹ and 0.019 s⁻¹. This study showcases the potential of scCO₂ extraction for the recycling of electrolyte solvents from LiB waste. Moreover, it guides towards environmental-friendly recycling solutions within the circular economy of battery electrolyte components.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Nils Zachmann: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Burçak Ebin:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Conceptualization.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests: Burçak Ebin reports financial support was provided by Horizon Europe. Burçak Ebin reports financial support was provided by Swedish Research Council Formas. If there are other authors, they declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supporting information

Supplementary data associated with this article can be found in the online version at [doi:10.1016/j.jcou.2025.103145](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcou.2025.103145).

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

References

- B. Niu, Z. Xu, J. Xiao, Y. Qin, Recycling hazardous and valuable electrolyte in spent Lithium-Ion batteries: urgency, progress, challenge, and viable approach, *Chem. Rev.* 123 (2023) 8718–8735, <https://doi.org/10.1021/ACS.CHEMREV.3C00174/ASSET/IMAGES/LARGE/CR3C00174.0008.JPEG>.
- S. Bertilsson, F. Larsson, M. Furlani, I. Albinsson, B.E. Mellander, Lithium-ion battery electrolyte emissions analyzed by coupled thermogravimetric/Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy, *J. Power Sources* 365 (2017) 446–455, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpowsour.2017.08.082>.
- A. Nedjalkov, J. Meyer, M. Köhring, A. Doering, M. Angelmahr, S. Dahle, A. Sander, A. Fischer, W. Schade, Toxic gas emissions from damaged lithium ion batteries—analysis and safety enhancement solution, *Batteries* 2 (2016) 5, <https://doi.org/10.3390/batteries2010005>.
- J. Marshall, D. Gastol, R. Sommerville, B. Middleton, V. Goodship, E. Kendrick, Disassembly of li ion cells—characterization and safety considerations of a recycling scheme, *Metals (Basel)* 10 (2020) 773, <https://doi.org/10.3390/met10060773>.
- N.P. Lebedeva, L. Boon-Brett, Considerations on the chemical toxicity of contemporary Li-Ion battery electrolytes and their components, *J. Electrochem. Soc.* 163 (2016) A821–A830, <https://doi.org/10.1149/2.0171606jes>.
- F. Diaz, Y. Wang, R. Weyhe, B. Friedrich, Gas generation measurement and evaluation during mechanical processing and thermal treatment of spent Li-ion batteries, *Waste Manag* 84 (2019) 102–111, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wasman.2018.11.029>.
- Battery-related waste codes update set to boost circular economy - European Commission, (n.d.). (https://environment.ec.europa.eu/news/battery-related-waste-codes-update-set-boost-circular-economy-2025-03-05_en) (accessed April 24, 2025).
- G. Harper, Roadmap for a sustainable circular economy in lithium-ion and future battery technologies, *J. Phys. Energy* 5 (2022) 021501, <https://doi.org/10.1088/2515-7655/aca57>.
- J. Neumann, M. Petranikova, M. Meeus, J.D. Gamarra, R. Younesi, M. Winter, S. Nowak, Recycling of Lithium-Ion Batteries-Current State of the Art, *Circular Economy, and Next Generation Recycling*, 2102917 (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1002/aenm.202102917>.
- N. Zachmann, M. Petranikova, B. Ebin, Electrolyte recovery from spent lithium-ion batteries using a low temperature thermal treatment process, *J. Ind. Eng. Chem.* 118 (2022) 351–361, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jiec.2022.11.020>.
- F. Larsson, S. Bertilsson, M. Furlani, I. Albinsson, B.E. Mellander, Gas explosions and thermal runaways during external heating abuse of commercial lithium-ion graphite-LiCoO₂ cells at different levels of ageing, *J. Power Sources* 373 (2018) 220–231, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpowsour.2017.10.085>.
- S. Nowak, M. Winter, The role of sub- and supercritical CO₂ as “processing solvent” for the recycling and sample preparation of lithium ion battery electrolytes, *Molecules* 22 (2017) 403, <https://doi.org/10.3390/molecules22030403>.
- K. He, Z.Y. Zhang, L. Alai, F.S. Zhang, A Green process for exfoliating electrode materials and simultaneously extracting electrolyte from spent lithium-ion batteries, *J. Hazard. Mater.* 375 (2019) 43–51, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhazmat.2019.03.120>.
- P. Haas, S. Pfeifer, J. Müller, C. Bradtmöller, S. Scholl, Separation of the electrolyte—solvent extraction. *Sustain. Prod. Life Cycle Eng. Manag.*, Springer, 2018, pp. 155–176, https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-70572-9_9.
- N. Zachmann, R.V. Fox, M. Petranikova, B. Ebin, Implementation of a sub-and supercritical carbon dioxide process for the selective recycling of the electrolyte from spent Li-ion battery, *J. CO₂ Util.* 81 (2024) 102703, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcou.2024.102703>.
- S. Lee, Green chemistry and chemical engineering, vii–viii, Part. Technol. Appl. (2016). <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4939-9060-3>.
- P. Raveendran, Y. Ikushima, S.L. Wallen, Polar attributes of supercritical carbon dioxide, *Acc. Chem. Res.* 38 (2005) 478–485, <https://doi.org/10.1021/ar040082m>.
- M.D.L. de Castro, M. Valcárcel, M.T. Tena, Analytical supercritical fluid extraction, Springer Berlin Heidelberg, 1994, <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-78673-0>.
- F. Ingresso, M.F. Ruiz-López, Modeling solvation in supercritical CO₂, *ChemPhysChem* 18 (2017) 2560–2572, <https://doi.org/10.1002/cphc.201700434>.
- S. Shimizu, S. Abbott, How entrainers enhance solubility in supercritical carbon dioxide, *J. Phys. Chem. B* 120 (2016) 3713–3723, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jpcc.6b01380>.
- M. Grütze, V. Kraft, W. Weber, C. Wendt, A. Friesen, S. Klamor, M. Winter, S. Nowak, Supercritical carbon dioxide extraction of lithium-ion battery electrolytes, *J. Supercrit. Fluids* 94 (2014) 216–222, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.supflu.2014.07.014>.
- M. Grütze, X. Mönnighoff, F. Horsthemke, V. Kraft, M. Winter, S. Nowak, Extraction of lithium-ion battery electrolytes with liquid and supercritical carbon dioxide and additional solvents, *RSC Adv.* 5 (2015) 43209–43217, <https://doi.org/10.1039/c5ra04451k>.
- Y. Liu, D. Mu, R. Zheng, C. Dai, Supercritical CO₂ extraction of organic carbonate-based electrolytes of lithium-ion batteries, *RSC Adv.* 4 (2014) 54525–54531, <https://doi.org/10.1039/c4ra10530c>.
- W.E. Org, Y. Liu, D. Mu, Y. Dai, Q. Ma, R. Zheng, C. Dai, Analysis on extraction behaviour of Lithium-ion battery electrolyte solvents in supercritical CO₂ by gas chromatography, *Int. J. Electrochem. Sci.* 11 (2016) 7594–7604, <https://doi.org/10.20964/2016.09.03>.
- Y. Liu, D. Mu, R. Li, Q. Ma, R. Zheng, C. Dai, Purification and characterization of reclaimed electrolytes from spent Lithium-Ion batteries, *J. Phys. Chem. C* 121 (2017) 4181–4187, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jpcc.6b12970>.
- X. Mönnighoff, A. Friesen, B. Konersmann, F. Horsthemke, M. Grütze, M. Winter, S. Nowak, Supercritical carbon dioxide extraction of electrolyte from spent lithium ion batteries and its characterization by gas chromatography with chemical ionization, *J. Power Sources* 352 (2017) 56–63, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpowsour.2017.03.114>.
- D. Mu, Y. Liu, R. Li, Q. Ma, C. Dai, Transcritical CO₂ extraction of electrolytes for lithium-ion batteries: optimization of the recycling process and quality-quantity variation, *N. J. Chem.* 41 (2017) 7177–7185, <https://doi.org/10.1039/c7nj00771j>.
- S. Sloop, L. Crandon, M. Allen, K. Koetje, L. Reed, L. Gaines, W. Sirisaksoontorn, M. Lerner, A direct recycling case study from a lithium-ion battery recall, *Sustain. Mater. Technol.* 25 (2020) e00152, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.susmat.2020.e00152>.

- [29] H. Sovová, Mathematical model for supercritical fluid extraction of natural products and extraction curve evaluation, *J. Supercrit. Fluids* 33 (2005) 35–52, <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.SUPFLU.2004.03.005>.
- [30] V. Abrahamsson, N. Andersson, B. Nilsson, C. Turner, Method development in inverse modeling applied to supercritical fluid extraction of lipids, *J. Supercrit. Fluids* 111 (2016) 14–27, <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.SUPFLU.2016.01.006>.
- [31] Z. Huang, X. Han Shi, W. Juan Jiang, Theoretical models for supercritical fluid extraction, *J. Chromatogr. A* 1250 (2012) 2–26, <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.CHROMA.2012.04.032>.
- [32] J.M. Del Valle, F.A. Urrego, Free solute content and solute-matrix interactions affect apparent solubility and apparent solute content in supercritical CO2 extractions. a hypothesis paper, *J. Supercrit. Fluids* 66 (2012) 157–175, <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.SUPFLU.2011.10.006>.
- [33] J.-C. Tedjar, Farouk; Foudraz, Method for the mixed recycling of lithium-based anode batteries and cells, USA Pat. 7.820.317 B2. (2010).
- [34] C. Peschel, S. van Wickeren, Y. Preibisch, V. Naber, D. Werner, L. Frankenstein, F. Horsthemke, U. Peucker, M. Winter, S. Nowak, Comprehensive characterization of shredded Lithium-ion battery recycling material, *Chem. A Eur. J.* 28 (2022) e202200485, <https://doi.org/10.1002/CHEM.202200485>.
- [35] J. Henschel, C. Peschel, S. Klein, F. Horsthemke, M. Winter, S. Nowak, Clarification of decomposition pathways in a state-of-the-art lithium ion battery electrolyte through ¹³C-Labeling of electrolyte components, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* 59 (2020) 6128–6137, <https://doi.org/10.1002/anie.202000727>.
- [36] N. Saqib, C.M. Ganim, A.E. Shelton, J.M. Porter, On the decomposition of carbonate-based lithium-ion battery electrolytes studied using operando infrared spectroscopy, *J. Electrochem. Soc.* 165 (2018) A4051–A4057, <https://doi.org/10.1149/2.1051816jes>.
- [37] C. Schultz, S. Vedder, M. Winter, S. Nowak, Qualitative investigation of the decomposition of organic solvent based lithium ion battery electrolytes with LC-IT-TOF-MS, *Anal. Chem.* 88 (2016) 11160–11168, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.analchem.6b03379>.
- [38] D. Hubble, D.E. Brown, Y. Zhao, C. Fang, J. Lau, B.D. McCloskey, G. Liu, Liquid electrolyte development for low-temperature lithium-ion batteries, *Energy Environ. Sci.* 15 (2022) 550–578, <https://doi.org/10.1039/d1ee01789f>.
- [39] K. Xu, Nonaqueous liquid electrolytes for lithium-based rechargeable batteries, *Chem. Rev.* 104 (2004) 4303–4417, <https://doi.org/10.1021/cr030203g>.
- [40] K. Abe, Nonaqueous Electrolytes and Advances in Additives, (2014) 167–207. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4939-0302-3_3.
- [41] J. Diekmann, C. Hanisch, L. Froböse, G. Schällicke, T. Loellhoeffel, A.-S. Fölster, A. Kwade, Ecological recycling of lithium-ion batteries from electric vehicles with focus on mechanical processes, *J. Electrochem. Soc.* 164 (2017) A6184–A6191, <https://doi.org/10.1149/2.0271701jes>.
- [42] J. Xiao, T. Zhou, R. Shen, Z. Xu, Migration and Transformation Mechanism of Toxic Electrolytes During Mechanical Treatment of Spent Lithium-Ion Batteries, *ACS Sustain.*
- [43] J. Henschel, F. Horsthemke, Y.P. Stenzel, M. Evertz, S. Girod, C. Lürenbaum, K. Kösters, S. Wiemers-Meyer, M. Winter, S. Nowak, Lithium ion battery electrolyte degradation of field-tested electric vehicle battery cells – a comprehensive analytical study, *J. Power Sources* 447 (2020) 227370, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpowsour.2019.227370>.
- [44] S.J. Jethwa, L.A. Román-Ramírez, P.A. Anderson, G.A. Leeke, Vapor equilibrium data for the binary mixtures of dimethyl carbonate and ethyl methyl carbonate in compressed carbon dioxide, *Int. J. Thermophys.* 44 (2023) 1–13, <https://doi.org/10.1007/S10765-023-03186-2/FIGURES/4>.
- [45] C.H. Cheng, Y.P. Chen, Vapor–liquid equilibria of carbon dioxide with isopropyl acetate, diethyl carbonate and ethyl butyrate at elevated pressures, *Fluid Phase Equilib.* 234 (2005) 77–83, <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.FLUID.2005.05.018>.
- [46] M.H. Lee, J.H. Yim, J.W. Kang, J.S. Lim, Measurement of VLE data of carbon dioxide + dimethyl carbonate system for the direct synthesis of dimethyl carbonate using supercritical CO2 and methanol, *Fluid Phase Equilib.* 318 (2012) 77–82, <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.FLUID.2012.01.020>.
- [47] N. Zachmann, C. Cicconardi, B. Ebin, Exploring the solubility of ethylene carbonate in supercritical carbon dioxide: a pathway for sustainable electrolyte recycling from Li-ion batteries, 2025, Vol. 11, Page 98, *Batter* 11 (2025) 98, <https://doi.org/10.3390/BATTERIES11030098>.
- [48] D. Kajiya, M. Imanishi, K.I. Saitow, Solvation of esters and ketones in supercritical CO2, *J. Phys. Chem. B* 120 (2016) 785–792, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jpcc.5b11740>.
- [49] Ž. Knez, C. Lütge, Product, process and plant design using subcritical and supercritical fluids for industrial application, *Prod. Process Plant Des. Using Subcritical Supercrit. Fluids Ind. Appl.* (2023) 1–256, <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-34636-1/COVER>.
- [50] H. Sovová, Apparent solubility of natural products extracted with near-critical carbon dioxide, *Am. J. Anal. Chem.* 2012 (2012) 958–965, <https://doi.org/10.4236/AJAC.2012.312A127>.
- [51] R.B. Gupta, J.J. Shim, Solubility in supercritical carbon dioxide, solubility supercrit, *Carbon Dioxide* (2006) 1–909, <https://doi.org/10.1201/9781420005998/SOLUBILITY-SUPERCritical-CARBON-DIOXIDE-RAM-GUPTA-JAE-JIN-SHIM>.